

METHODS AND TECHNOLOGY OF APPLE DRYING

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Annotation: In our country, special attention is paid to increasing the volume of agricultural production. This is because agricultural products are the mainstay of the country's food security, the main raw material for industrial production. In recent years, as a result of optimizing the composition of arable land, the area of orchards has expanded. The introduction of new and advanced technologies in production is underway. The geographical zone of the republic is very suitable for growing sweet fruits. However, the cultivation of fruits is seasonal and their long-term storage is limited. In particular, due to the delicate nature of apples from seeded fruits, there are serious shortcomings in their cultivation and storage. Therefore, most of the grown fruits are sent for immediate processing. However, the issues of product processing have not been sufficiently studied on a scientific basis. Therefore, scientific and technical achievements and best practices in this area are not widely used in production. At present, processing enterprises are formed mainly on a private basis, and their production is carried out using the simplest technologies. Also, processed products made from fruits grown in our country are highly valued in the world market. This is an urgent need to improve processing methods, introduce new modern technologies and develop the processing of fruit products. This requires the study, knowledge and application of agricultural processing technologies, in particular apples. In this way, the population can be provided with a variety of vitamins, carbohydrates, mineral salts and other essential substances throughout the year.

Alternative drying procedures of each type have been developed to obtain high quality dried products. During drying, a large amount of moisture is lost over a period of time, and the quality of the raw material is almost unchanged. After cooking, the quality of the product returns to its original state. With the right drying technology, the main nutrients in the fruit are well preserved, and the calories are increased by 10-30 times as a result of the loss of excess moisture. The product is dried in two main ways: artificially and naturally. There are

several types of artificial drying methods, including low pressure, spray dryers, and hot bed drying.

Sublimation drying is a promising method based on the loss of moisture in the product at low pressure. In this case, the raw materials in vegetables and fruits are preserved almost unchanged and, after soaking, retain their properties close to their original state. For drying, it is better to use varieties that are rich in drying agents. Apples are usually cut into flat pieces and dried.

The most important thing in preparation for drying is blanching. Instead of blanching, apples are treated by burning sulfur dioxide or immersing them in a liquid mixture.

Drying in the sun. In Uzbekistan, most fruits are dried in the sun. In cloudless, hot, sunny weather, it is possible to carry out drying for several days without consuming excess fuel and electricity for the technological process.

Drying sites are located close to gardens and vineyards. Areas should be well ventilated and sunny.

For every square meter of area, 14-16 kg of dried apples and 10-12 kg of apples cut into two or four can be dried. Apples cut into two or four pieces are ready in 8-20 days, those treated with alkaline solution in 10-12 days, and those not treated in 30 days. Fruits and grapes are actually dried twice. for the first time fruit type

from 1-2 days to 5-6 days, depending on the position of the sun.

The next time the moisture escapes, the pads are placed on stacks and dried for 4-10 days. In the drying area, the trays are placed on the ground, one pair at a time, or one at a time. a 0.6-meter-wide corridor will be left between the two rows of paddles. the paddles are stacked on the stacks in order to dry the damp fruits properly. Apple varieties (Saratoni variety, Borovinka tashkentskaya variety, Afrosiabi variety, Aydin variety) "varieties. The well-ripened fruit is cut to obtain a high quality dry product. The method of drying it is no different from making apple peel.

Depending on the size of the apple, the fruit is washed well, then the large ones are cut into four pieces and the small ones into two pieces. then remove the core and the bandana from the middle and cook in boiling water for 2-3 minutes. then rinse with clean, running water. per kilogram of fruit is consumed 2-3 grams of sulfur and smoked for 1.5-2 hours. Smoked apples are placed on the stalks in the drying area and dried in the sun for 4-5 days. After 2-3 days the fruits are rolled out. then the padnis are shaded and dried in stacks. Apples are dried for 12-18 days. 14-18% of it is extracted. its humidity should not exceed 24%. The

well-dried stalks include light yellow snake. Moisture leveling, boxing, and storage are no different from apple peel storage methods.

Prior to packaging, the dried fruit is sorted according to the quality of the dry product and passed through a magnetic separator, which traps any metal particles that have fallen. The dry products are packed in 12.5 kg corrugated cardboard boxes, 25 11 kg plywood boxes, 25 kg plywood drums according to GOST 12003-66. Dried apples can be packed in cloth bags of 30-50 kg, in paper bags of 25 kg. Prior to packaging, the boxes are lined with paraffin paper, as there should be no gaps after the product is placed, it should be well wrapped and impermeable to moisture. Special presses are used to tightly place dry products in the boxes. Dried fruits are stored in special boxes or kraft bags. The mouth is tightly closed and placed on clean dry shelves is set. The first shelf is 10 cm above the ground. walls and shelves A 0.5-meter road will be left between the rows and one central (1.5-1.8-meter) side road will be left between the rows. The maximum height of the shelves should be 2.5 meters to make the product easy to install and remove. There must be a corridor at the entrance to the built rooms. The product is divided into shelves, batches and varieties. each batch of product must have a passport or label. it must contain the name of the product, brand, weight, date of manufacture and acceptance.

